

THE IMPACT OF TEACHING STRATEGIES ON CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola o'quvchilarning ta'lim olishi hamda xulq-atvoriga ta'lim jarayonini ta'sir qilishida samarali sinf strategiyalarning muhimligini ta'kidlaydi. Bundan tashqari, ta'lim nazariyalarining integratsiyalashuviga urg'u beradi va ijobiy sinf madaniyatini rivojlantirish va professional xulq-atvorni modellashtirish muhimligini ta'kidlaydi.

Аннотация. В этой статье подчеркивается важность эффективных стратегий управления классом, влияющих на обучение и поведение учащихся. В нем подчеркивается интеграция образовательных теорий и подчеркивается важность формирования позитивной культуры в классе и моделирования профессионального поведения.

Annotation. This article highlights the importance of effective classroom management strategies in influencing student learning and behavior. It emphasizes the integration of educational theories and it stresses the importance of fostering a positive classroom culture and modeling professional behavior.

Kalit so'zlar. Sinfni boshqarish, xulq-atvor, boshqaruv uslublari, aniq qoidalar, o'z-o'zini nazorat qilish, ijobiy sinf madaniyati, loyiha asosida o'rganish, o'quvchilarning mustaqilligi, o'qituvchining ta'siri, o'quvchilarning xatti-harakati.

Ключевые слова. Управление классом, поведение, стили управления, четкие правила, самоконтроль, позитивная культура класса, проектное обучение, независимость учащихся, влияние учителя, движение за поведение учащихся.

Key words. Classroom management, behaviorism, management styles, clear rules, self-monitoring, positive classroom culture, project-based learning, student independence, teacher influence, student behaviour.

Teachers' strategies for managing a classroom environment have evolved over time, influenced by educational theories, psychological research, and practical experiences in the classroom. Early educational theories, like the principles of behaviorism, particularly the work of B.F. Skinner[6;78], emphasized the use of

reinforcement and punishment to shape student behavior. This led to strategies such as positive reinforcement and behavior modification techniques. And another theories of Jean Piaget and Lev Vygotsky [6;78]highlighted the importance of active learning and social interaction, influencing strategies that promote student engagement and collaboration.

The teacher is an integral figure in the overall running and management of the classroom. “When teachers do not want to learn, it is obvious that the students are not going to learn either.”[10;208] This suggests that the way in which the teacher plans and leads the classroom will have a dramatic effect on the student’s academic achievement. If a teacher is not fully engaged and excited about what they are teaching then the children will pick up on this and not be engaged to learn as much as they could be. An effective teacher often becomes a professional leader who thinks, reflects and implements [10; 208]. This leadership role has several qualities that will help to oversee the running of a classroom. Some of these qualities might include having plans, goals and vision, motivates and inspires others, works well with others, well prepared, passionate about what they are doing and focused. Many teachers have different management styles that they prefer to use on a day-to-day basis. This will be due to individual preference, personality and values of the teacher. Levin and Nolan suggests that there are many different teaching strategies and management styles that teachers can use to promote good classroom management. They suggest three ways in which the class can be managed; student directed management, collaborative management and teacher directed management [9; 208]. The purpose of the student directed approach is to build and create a community of learners in which they work productively together and care for one another. This would mean that in a collaborative classroom, the learning process is joint with student and teacher. Similar to the student directed approach; students are given a chance to control their own behavior. This gives students a chance to be responsible for their own learning process and behaviour [10;209]. Within a teacher directed management style classroom, the teacher will have sole responsibility for what is going on in the classroom and how the children are learning and behaving. This strategy could be helpful for some learning environments in which teacher direction is needed.

Well-constructed rules are essential to an efficient classroom environment and as a factor in reducing incidents of misbehavior. Levin and Nolan, state “ Evidence indicates that children in general and children who exhibit disruptive behavior in particular are highly sensitive to changing situations and conditions. Given this, the need for rules is apparent.” [6;77]“Clear rules provide consistency in the classroom. Students prefer knowing the rules, consequences and rewards rather than having a teacher who arbitrarily changes or makes up new rules to fit the moment.” [2; 268] Jones and Jones, also go on to suggest that helping students understand and accept classroom and whole school rules can provide benefit students and teaching [3;695]. Another important aspect, which relates to the development of rules in the classroom, is the use of self-monitoring techniques. Jones and Jones, suggest that rules should help students to choose appropriate behaviors rather than being used as a means of catching the student out misbehaving [3;700]. When a student misbehave teachers should discuss with the child about what they have done examining the motivation behind their actions and the consequences. This is a powerful technique to help students overcome behavioural issues because if students are encouraged to examine the motivations behind their behaviour as well as the consequences of their actions then they are less likely to dwell on the negative aspects of behavior [4; 1023]. This idea can be linked to the Jean Piaget’s theory of children’s moral development. Piaget

proposed that children go through a number of different stages as the develop morality [5;46].

When it comes to the teacher's role in the classroom, a number of teacher roles are explored below, based on teachers' beliefs and assumptions on they work.

1. Teacher as Career. Teachers are required to create safe learning environments that are respectful and inclusive for the learning benefit of their students. Being kind, empathetic and understanding are only some of the character traits that create this safe learning space. While promoting learning, it also allows teachers the opportunity to connect with students individually. Effective instruction requires teachers to have a solid understanding of their students, to know how they learn and to know what they are interested in. By acknowledging that all students approach learning differently with a variety of preferences for instruction [6;2] teachers are able to plan lessons to maximise engagement and promote autonomy and ownership of learning, where students choose excellence and mastery as their educational outcome [10;160]. Arguably, the ability to learn independently is the primary aim of instructional education, regardless of the year level. However, independence is a learnt process that occurs through careful scaffolded support. Educators ensure students have adequate support to achieve the learning objectives, then gradually fade or remove the scaffolds as students begin to take more responsibility for their own learning [9;32]. To ensure scaffolds are effective, teachers are required.

2. Teacher as Role Model. Aligned to Vygotsky’s view that positive social interactions enhance cognitive development [8;3], it is imperative for teachers to foster authentic, respectful relationships within the classroom. Teachers are responsible for modelling acceptable forms of communication, both verbally and non-verbally and to explicitly communicate expectations regarding mutual care and respect of others. Developing social competencies, friendships and peer acceptance promotes higher levels of classroom participation, motivation and resiliency. To safeguard against harassment, bullying, racism, negative stereotypes and abuse, it is a teacher’s responsibility to critically examine their own stereotypes and prejudicial attitudes, and to be aware of any underlying adverse attitudes existing within the classroom. Teachers and students alike need to work collaboratively and cooperatively in a shared environment that values differences and rewards interest in others. Teachers’ professionalism in thought, action and communication are not negotiable expectations and requirements in their role as educators. On a daily basis, teachers model ideal and appropriate responses to their peers, parents and students, as their reactions and inactions, responses and negotiations, are all witnessed and relay messages. Teacher actions reinforce and set the expectation of student behaviour: if teachers are disorganised, late to class, and ill-prepared, they cannot expect the opposite from their students if this is their modelled behaviour.

Additionally, building a positive classroom culture is also crucial because teachers serve as role models for their students. By consistently demonstrating behaviours such as punctuality, preparedness, and respect, teachers set a standard for students to emulate. This modeling extends beyond academic expectations to social interactions and problem-solving approaches. Moreover, understanding students' personal backgrounds and challenges can significantly impact classroom management and empathy helps in forming stronger connections with students, making them feel valued and understood, which in turn can reduce behavioural issues. Effective communication can help to see the diverse needs of students. This includes using clear, concise language, non-verbal cues, and being mindful of students' individual communication styles. Adaptive communication ensures that instructions are understood and followed, minimizing confusion and disruption.

Enhancing student engagement is one of the teacher's strategies that they can use in the classroom environment, by incorporating game elements into the classroom and this can increase student motivation and engagement. Strategies such as point systems, leaderboards, and rewards for academic achievements can make learning more interactive and enjoyable. Another strategy is project-based learning, which means engaging students in projects that require critical thinking, collaboration, and problem-solving can keep them invested in their learning. Project-based learning allows students to explore real-world problems and develop solutions, making their learning experience more relevant and meaningful. Student Autonomy in some cases is necessary because, giving students independence in their learning process can boost their engagement and responsibility. This can include involving them in setting classroom rules, choosing project topics, or selecting how they will demonstrate their learning.

In conclusion, the strategies teachers use to manage their classrooms are crucial for shaping how well students learn and behave. By drawing on various educational theories and practical experiences, effective classroom management combines ideas from behaviorism, constructivism, and social learning. Teachers influence student engagement and behavior through different management styles, whether they direct the classroom themselves or let students take more control. Clear rules and self-monitoring help keep things consistent and encourage good behavior. Creating a positive classroom culture and modeling professional behavior and using strategies like project-based learning, and giving students more independence can boost motivation and engagement are key elements for managing students. Ultimately, the success of these strategies depends on the teacher's ability to meet the diverse needs of their students, creating a respectful and dynamic learning environment.

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